

THE EFFECT OF STRATEGIC ALIGNMENT ON PURCHASING MANAGEMENT

ABSTRACT

Purpose- The aim of this research is to analyze the role of the strategic integration of the purchasing function in the relationship between well-established practices and performance in that function. We argue that the strategic integration of purchasing may have effects (effect direct, effect mediating, effect moderating) on the operating performance of the purchasing function

Design/methodology/approach- Our propositions derived from the key studies about strategic and advanced purchasing practices are tested with data from 156 industrial companies using Structural Equation Modelling methodology.

Findings- The results suggest that the role of purchasing strategic integration consists of a mediated effect on purchasing performance through the implementation of certain advanced practices. We also conclude that strategic integration as well as the implementation of these advanced purchasing practices favour the implementation of differentiation strategies based on quality, dependability and flexibility rather than the implementation of cost leadership strategies.

Research limitations/implications- Although it is a common practice in operations management research, the use of perceptual measures obtained from a single informant constitutes a noteworthy limitation. Future research could make an effort to combine different sources of information and to identify and use more objective indicators.

Practical implications- Top managers should take into account the need to involve the purchasing function in the strategic planning process of the firm.

Originality/value- The results not only confirm findings from previous literature as to the strategic relevance of the purchasing function, but they also help to clarify the mechanisms which make this integration important.

KEY WORDS: Strategic alignment of purchasing, Logistic practices, Supplier involvement, Purchasing management performance.

THE ROLE OF STRATEGIC INTEGRATION IN PURCHASING FUNCTION PERFORMANCE

1. Introduction

The strategic importance given to the purchasing function is considered a response to the various competitive market pressures (Pressey et al., 2009) or the result of the professionalization of purchasing and the work of the associations created by these professionals (Ferguson et al. 1996). In any case, it has become clear in recent years that the weight of purchasing in the strategic planning process is becoming more and more important and that it has positive effects on the performance of the purchasing function and, consequently, on business performance (Carr and Smeltzer, 1997; Narasimham and Das, 2001; Cousins, 2005, Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009; Prajogo, et al. 2011).

In order to assess the extent to which this strategic positioning of the purchasing function takes place in an organization, Narasimham and Das, 2001 (pp. 593) introduced the concept of the strategic integration of purchasing, which they called ‘purchasing integration’ and defined as the integration and alignment of strategic purchasing practices and goals with those of the firm. A similar concept is “strategic purchasing” (e.g. Carr and Pearson, 2002; Chen et al., 2004): the alignment of objectives in the purchasing function with the rest of the organization facilitates the activation of the competences of purchasing function within the company and strengthens its status (Carr and Smeltzer, 1997). In this line, Van-Weele (2000) argues that the strategic alignment of the purchasing function with other functions translates into greater efficiency (in terms of costs, quality and logistics), and greater efficacy. Therefore, the strategic integration of purchasing can be a powerful instrument in the scope and control of supply chain objectives and equally a determinant tool to improve purchasing performance.

Nevertheless, even if we recognize that the strategic integration of purchasing has positive effects on the organization, it is important to determine the mechanisms through which this effect takes place. In this respect, Narasimhan and Das (2001) analyzed the role of the strategic integration of purchasing in the relation between purchasing practices and manufacturing performance. They analyzed the possibility of a direct effect on

manufacturing performance, as well as that of an indirect effect on performance through the purchasing practices and a moderating effect on the relation between purchasing practices and performance. The empirical results of this analysis favoured the third option. Following the same method, this paper tries to analyze the role of the strategic integration of purchasing in the relation between purchasing practices and purchasing function performance. Equally, there appear three possibilities that are then analyzed empirically. The main difference with Narasimhan and Das's (2001) paper is that we adopt an intra-functional rather than an inter-functional approach, that is to say, we fundamentally focus on the effects that the strategic integration of purchasing has on the operation and performance of the purchasing function, without assessing the effect that it could have on the results of other functional areas or of the organization overall. This leads us to bear in mind other effects of the strategic integration of purchasing different to that of the vertical (between business and functional strategies) and horizontal (between functional strategies) alignment, such as the greater availability of resources in the purchasing function derived from its top status inside the organization.

2. Advanced Purchasing Practices: Initial Hypothesis

The changing role of purchasing has resulted in the emergence of new forms of relationships with suppliers, which abandoned the traditional interpretation of them as “adversaries” (Helper, 1991) and established new ways of working together. In this sense, Dyer and Singh (1998) argue that companies willing to share knowledge and resources will generate higher incomes than they could obtain individually. Under this premise, many companies have striven to develop a climate of trust and cooperation with their suppliers to enhance longer-term contracts and a more fluid exchange of information with a reduced base of suppliers.

This new scenario has led to the development of a series of purchasing management practices that challenge the traditional or competitive paradigm and that, for that reason, we have labelled as ‘advanced’ and classified into three categories: control practices, involvement practices, and logistic practices. Some representative practices within each group and some articles that have referred to them with equivalent terminology are shown in Table I.

Table I: Advanced purchasing practices

	PURCHASING PRACTICES	AUTOR
CONTROL PRACTICES	Formal evaluation of suppliers' capacities and performance	Krause and Ellram (1997), Enarsson, (1998), Carr and Pearson (1999), Krause (1999), Narasimhan and Das (2001), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006).
	Quality certifications required of suppliers	Carr and Pearson (1999), Krause (1999), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005).
	Quality testing of purchased materials	Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006).
	Monitoring and controlling the key suppliers' operation	Carr and Pearson (1999), Kannan and Choon (2006), Wagner (2006).
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT PRACTICES	Key suppliers are involved in improving product design	Narasimhan and Das (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Paulraj et al., (2006). Carr et al., 2008.
	Supplier involvement in the design and development of new products	Narasimhan and Das (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004), Hemsworth et al. (2005), Sánchez-Rodríguez et al. (2005), Paulraj et al., (2006), Carr et al., 2008
	Suppliers help solve problems in the company's production processes	Krause (1999), Krause (1999), Giménez and Ventura (2005), Paulraj et al., (2006).
	Suppliers involved in the design of the company's logistics system	Chen and Paulraj (2004), Giménez and Ventura (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Paulraj et al., (2006), Oh and Rhee, (2008).
LOGISTIC PRACTICES	Coordination of manufacturing plans and production lines between suppliers and buyers	Frohlich and Westbrook (2001), Giménez and Ventura (2005), Kannan and Choon (2006), Paulraj et al., (2006). Oh and Rhee, (2008).
	Adaptation of suppliers' delivery frequencies to buyers' requirements in small batches	Frohlich and Westbrook (2001), Chen and Paulraj (2004), Paulraj et al., (2006), Demeter and Matyusz 2011).
	Coordination of transportation and storage capacity among suppliers and buyers	Chen and Paulraj (2004), Paulraj et al., (2006).
	Coordination in the use of containers and equipment between suppliers and buyers	Frohlich and Westbrook (2001), Paulraj et al., (2006).

Several studies have emphasized the positive impact that the implementation of these practices has on the organization (e.g. Kannan and Choon, 2006; Paulraj et al., 2006; Modi and Mabert, 2007; Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009; Prajogo et al., 2011). Krause (1999) concluded that control practices such as the assessment and certification of suppliers ensure the regular and systematized implementation of quality standards on inputs, thus improving the overall quality of the product. Carr and Pearson (1999) stress that involvement practices such as exchange of personnel with suppliers or the training of these personnel can generate lower costs, better quality and greater co-ordination leading to greater flexibility and reliability. Greater coordination and logistics integration enables companies to achieve reductions in costs and delivery times (Stock et al., 1998; Chen and Paulraj, 2004; Giménez and Ventura, 2005, Oh y Rhee, 2008). According to this literature, we propose the following hypothesis:

H1: The implementation of advanced purchasing management practices is positively related to purchasing function performance.

3. The role of the strategic integration of the purchasing function

3.1. Direct effect of strategic integration on purchasing performance

The strategic integration of the purchasing function is understood as an internal initiative that concentrates a series of steps allowing the purchasing department to establish a link and coordinate their approaches with the individual goals and objectives of the other functional areas and with the organization as a whole. Some of these measures are the involvement of purchasing managers in the strategic planning process of the organization, the creation and establishment of a strategic purchasing plan based on the strategic business plan, the development of activities for disseminating and communicating the organizational strategy within the purchasing department, the involvement of the purchasing department in the cost policy of the firm, or the hiring, training and monitoring of the purchasing staff based on the strategic planning of the firm (Carr and Smeltzer, 1997, 1999; Narasimham and Das, 2001; Carr and Pearson, 2002; Paulraj et al., 2006).

According to Narasimhan and Das (2001), these measures represent a strategic bridge of communication with top management, drawing its attention to the need to allocate organizational resources to purchasing management. They also contribute to the development of active participation in the planning of new processes that directly or indirectly affect the operation of the purchasing department. Furthermore, these initiatives are a critical element for the effective development of strategic sourcing partnerships that are consistent with the organizational strategy (Zsidisin and Ellram, 2001; Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009), which will lead to more efficient and effective supply networks, thus improving the performance of the purchasing function. These arguments lead us to propose the following hypothesis:

H2: The strategic integration of the purchasing function has a positive and direct effect on the operational performance of the purchasing function

3.2 Indirect effect: the mediating role of advanced purchasing practices

The growing popularity of so-called advanced purchasing practices is due, among other things, to the greater recognition of the strategic role of purchasing, which has resulted in a commitment to practices of greater scope and impact. In fact, the introduction of advanced purchasing practices can be understood as an intermediate step necessary to achieve the effect of strategic integration on the purchasing function performance raised in the hypothesis above. Two arguments lead us to believe this. On the one hand, the transformation of the purchasing function to a more strategic approach is based on the belief that sourcing decisions can generate competitive advantages (Narasimhan and Das, 2001). This belief is often fuelled by the benefits attributed in recent years to advanced purchasing practices, which means that the strategic option posed in the purchasing function is in many cases a commitment to the implementation of more sophisticated practices, seeking to capture the positive effects attributed to them.

Furthermore, strategic integration recognizes the work and the importance of the purchasing function, giving greater provision for its development (Narasimhan and Das, 2001; Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009). That is, the purchasing function will have a greater organizational capacity to raise funds to enable it to implement more sophisticated

practices. It seems that the strategic integration of the purchasing function is associated with a greater development of this function, development that is manifested through the implementation of advanced practices. In this sense, Carr and Pearson (1999) argue that the participation of purchasing managers in the strategic planning process of the company can engage more appropriate processes and methods for selecting and evaluating suppliers, thus giving greater assurance of the fulfilment of the objectives of the organization.

According to the above, we propose the following hypothesis:

H3 The strategic integration of the purchasing function contributes positively to the implementation of advanced purchasing practices, such that the implementation of these practices mediates the relationship between strategic integration and purchasing function performance.

3.3 The moderating role of strategic integration

There are also arguments suggesting that the strategic integration of the purchasing function improves the operation of advanced purchasing practices, once they are in place, thus improving their effect on performance. That is, strategic integration positively moderates the effect of advanced practices on purchasing function performance that we suggested in hypothesis 1.

On the one hand, the greater the degree of strategic integration the greater the knowledge of the strategic guidelines at the business level and the initiatives undertaken by other functional areas. This ensures that those responsible for the implementation of advanced practices have updated information about the main changes and trends undertaken by the organization and can react in time, for example, by making changes in the operational control of suppliers, strengthening quality measures or introducing flexibility in delivery policies. This would bring about an improved effect of advanced purchasing practices since they have no conflict with other activities within the firm. This argument is consistent with the work of Pagell (2004), who states that a low level of strategic integration of the purchasing function often results in greater difficulty in solving problems, a poor exchange of information and low levels of performance.

On the other hand, the involvement of the purchasing function in the planning and allocation of resources enables the company to make further investments in that function. These investments not only enable the introduction of advanced purchasing practices, as argued in hypothesis 3, but they can also positively affect the training and abilities of the purchasing staff. This improved training will lead to better outcomes in the purchasing function. For example, better instruction in information and communication technologies can contribute to greater efficiency and effectiveness in supplier control (audits, evaluation, monitoring) and can facilitate supplier involvement and logistics coordination.

All these arguments lead us to propose the following hypothesis:

H4: The strategic integration of the purchasing function positively moderates the relationship between the implementation of advanced purchasing practices and purchasing function performance (that is, the greater the strategic integration of the purchasing function, the greater the effect of advanced practices on performance).

Figure 1 provides a graphical representation of the proposed hypotheses.

Figure 1: Initial Model: research hypothesis

4. Methodology

4.1. Data

The population chosen to test the hypotheses was comprised of all Spanish firms belonging to industrial sectors. These sectors are characterized by fully defined supply and logistical structures with noted relevance within the organization. To obtain information representative of this population, following the practice of other important researchers in this area (e.g. Carr and Pearson, 1999; Krause, 1999; Carr et al., 2000, Narasimhan and Das, 2001; Chen and Paulraj, 2004) we decided to send a questionnaire to members of an association of purchasing management.

The Spanish Association of Professionals of Purchasing and Supply Management (AERCE) agreed to cooperate in our research. This association had a total of 2459 members from industry, representing 71% of its total membership. For data collection a questionnaire was designed to be hosted on a web page whose link was sent through the newsletter of AERCE. Responses were received through an email and on an SQL database, also created exclusively for this research. This process yielded 156 correctly completed questionnaires, representing a response rate of 6.34%.

4.2. Measurements

Advanced Purchasing Practices. Purchasing managers were asked to assess on a 7- point Likert scale (from 1-never- to 7 -in all cases-), the level of implementation of a representative number of practices within each category considered in Figure 1 (control practices, participation and logistics). Confirmatory factor analysis was applied to check whether the three groups of practices constituted independent dimensions, but the results were unsatisfactory. This led us to conduct an exploratory factor analysis to try to determine whether the data corresponded to other factors not considered in the theoretical development. The result of this analysis, shown in Table II, revealed that the involvement practices load on two different factors: one capturing the supplier involvement in product design and the other the supplier involvement in the production process.

Table II: Advanced purchasing practices. Factor analyses

		EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS				CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS					
						F1	F2	F3	F4		
CONTROL PRACTICES											
ACTCONT1	Formal evaluation of suppliers' capacities and performance	0,168	0,743	0,020	0,196	0,652					
ACTCONT2	Quality certifications required of suppliers	-0,042	0,762	0,027	0,225	0,411					
ACTCONT3	Quality testing of purchased materials	0,290	0,599	0,315	-0,289	0,540					
ACTCONT4	Monitoring and controlling the key suppliers' operation	0,493	0,616	0,175	0,015	0,848					
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN											
ACTPAR1	Key suppliers are involved in improving product design	0,141	0,120	0,891	0,159	0,812					
ACTPAR2	Supplier involvement in the design and development of new products	0,223	0,093	0,882	0,183	0,939					
SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS											
ACTPAR3	Suppliers help solve problems of the company's production processes	0,193	0,070	0,294	0,705	0,755					
ACTPAR4	Suppliers involved in the design of the company's logistics system	0,189	0,197	0,083	0,849	0,718					
LOGISTICS PRACTICES											
ACTLOG1	Coordination of manufacturing plans and production lines between suppliers and buyers	0,641	0,273	0,162	0,189	0,678					
ACTLOG2	Adaptation of suppliers' delivery frequencies to buyers' requirements	0,836	0,125	0,089	0,015	0,713					
ACTLOG3	Coordination of transportation and storage capacity among suppliers and buyers	0,794	0,037	0,230	0,227	0,789					
ACTLOG4	Coordination in the use of containers and equipment between suppliers and buyers	0,574	0,107	0,076	0,432	0,606					
CRONBACH'S ALPHA						0,700	0,865	0,700	0,775		
F1: CONTROL PRACTICES		CORRELATIONS				F1	0,407***				
F2: SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN						F2					
F3: SUPPLIER INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS						F3				0,416***	0,503***
F4: LOGISITCS PRACTICES						F4				0,649***	0,515***
***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.10		VARIMAX ROTATION				INDEX	V.R.	VALUES OBTAINED			
		EXPLAINED VARIANCE: 68.52%				$\chi^2/g.l.$	≤ 3	2,139			
						p (χ^2)	>0,05	0,000			
						GFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,905			
						AGFI	$\geq 0,80$	0,845			
						TLI	$\geq 0,90$	0,884			
						CFI	$\geq 0,90$	0,916			

Again, we applied a confirmatory factor analysis to distinguish these two factors, (see Table II). The indices used to assess the adjustment of the proposed model to the structure of observed data reach recommended values or are very close to them. Each of the four factors has a Cronbach's alpha above 0.7, which denotes an acceptable level of reliability. Based on these results, it was considered that the measurement model distinguishing four factors had an acceptable fit. Therefore, by calculating the average of the items used for each factor, we built four measures of implementation of purchasing practices: control

practices, supplier involvement in product design, supplier involvement in production process and logistics practices.

Strategic Integration. Purchasing managers were asked to assess on a 7- point Likert scale (from 1-not at all, to 7-largely) to what degree a series of statements in Table III fit the situation of their companies. These items were taken from previous scales used in the literature (e.g. Carr and Smeltzer 1997; Carr and Smeltzer, 1999; Narasimhan and Das, 2001; Carr and Pearson, 2002). Principal components analysis was applied to verify the validity and one-dimensionality of the construct. All the items strongly load on the only factor with eigenvalue higher than 1, which is able to explain 68.91% of the variance (see Table III). Cronbach's α exceeds 0.9, which represents a high level of reliability.

Table III: Strategic integration of purchasing. Factor analysis

VARIABLE	PRACTICES	MEAN (S. D)	EXPLORATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS
IEST1	Purchasing professionals participate in the strategic planning process	5,10 (1,67)	0,742
IEST2	Strategic planning addresses the recruitment and training of purchasing staff	4,93 (1,53)	0,879
IEST3	The purchasing department has a good knowledge of the strategic business objectives	5,33 (1,36)	0,852
IEST4	Purchasing plans are continuously revised to adapt them to changes in strategic business planning	5,13 (1,61)	0,884
IEST5	The purchasing department participates in the design of cost policies	5,16 (1,60)	0,823
IEST6	The purchasing department makes decisions that correspond to the strategic objectives	5,00 (1,40)	0,792
EXPLAINED VARIANCE: 68,91%		CRONBACH's ALPHA 0,907	

Purchasing Operational Performance. Purchasing managers were asked to assess on a 7- point Likert scale (1-much worse-, 4-equal, 7-much better) the progress achieved in the last 3 years in the purchasing function for a number of issues listed in Table IV. According to Hemsworth et al. (2005) and Li et al. (2006), among others, the four competitive priorities raised by Wheelwright (1978) (quality, cost, dependability,

flexibility) are the most reliable to determine the performance of the purchasing function. According to this criterion, we selected three items referring to the quality objective, two items that refer to the cost objective, three to dependability and two to flexibility. A confirmatory factor analysis gave similar results to those obtained for advanced purchasing practices (see Table IV) and for the same reasons we believe that the observed data are in accordance with the model that distinguishes four competitive priorities or competitive objectives.

Table IV: Purchasing performance confirmatory factor analysis

		CONFIRMATORY FACTOR ANALYSIS			
		F1	F2	F3	F4
QUALITY					
PFC1	Reliability of purchased products	0,850			
PFC2	Fit between purchasing specifications and purchasing products (high finish, uniformity,...)	0,698			
PFC3	Efficacy of suppliers in attending to complaints	0,582			
COST					
PFC4	Cost of purchases		0,602		
PFC5	Low inventory levels		0,599		
DEPENDABILITY					
PFC6	Time needed to fulfil orders (lead time)			0,846	
PFC7	Fulfilment of agreed schedules by suppliers			0,857	
PFC8	Fulfilment of agreed delivery requirements by suppliers (quantity, quality, format,...)			0,879	
FLEXIBILITY					
PFC9	Supplier capability to introduce (customized) changes in products				0,880
PFC10	Supplier rate of introduction of new products (updated and leading products)				0,712
CRONBACH'S ALPHA		0,747	0,530	0,894	0,770
F1: QUALITY	CORRELATIONS	F1			
F2: COST		F2	0,745***		
F3: DEPENDABILITY		F3	0,836***	0,650***	
F4: FLEXIBILITY		F4	0,544***	0,363***	0,617***

***p<0,01 **p<0,05 *p<0,10

(Recommended values based on Chau ,1997)

INDEX	RECOMMENDED VALUE	VALUES OBTAINED
X ² /g.l.	≤ 3	1,726***
p (χ ²)	>0,05	0,009
GFI	≥ 0,90	0,942
AGFI	≥ 0,80	0,890
TLI	≥ 0,90	0,954
CFI	≥ 0,90	0,970

4.3. Analysis

To test hypotheses 1 and 2, regarding a direct relationship, we use Multiple Regression Analysis. In both cases, we estimated separate regression models for each dimension of performance as dependent variable and incorporated two control variables: firm size,

measured by a categorical variable that distinguishes four levels according to the number of employees (less than 50, between 50 and 100, between 100 and 500, and 500) and industrial sector, measured by a dichotomous variable that distinguishes the manufacturing from the extractive industry. With these two variables we intended to control the effect of economies of scale and the sector-specific features on purchasing function performance.

Table V: Regression of purchasing performance on advanced purchasing practices

	QUALITY						COST					
	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3	MODEL 4	MODEL 5	MODEL 6	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3	MODEL 4	MODEL 5	MODEL 6
CONSTANT	5,638***	4,957***	4,738***	4,722***	4,674 ***	4,965***	5,609***	5,226***	5,242***	5,303***	5,194***	5,303***
FIRM SIZE	(0,520)	(0,563)	(0,566)	(0,556)	(0,556)	(0,521)	(0,756)	(0,837)	(0,853)	(0,765)	(0,850)	(0,765)
TYPE OF INDUSTRY	0,037	0,005	-0,011	-0,018	-0,018	-0,003	-0,030	-0,048	-0,047	-0,053	-0,055	-0,053
CONTROL PRACTICES	(0,064)	(0,064)	(0,063)	(0,062)	(0,062)	(0,062)	(0,093)	(0,095)	(0,096)	(0,093)	(0,095)	(0,093)
INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN	-0,059	-0,074	-0,060	-0,133	-0,145	-0,167	-0,163	-0,171	-0,172	-0,242	-0,262	-0,242
INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS LOGISTICS PRACTICES	(0,264)	(0,259)	(0,255)	(0,253)	(0,253)	(0,252)	(0,384)	(0,384)	(0,385)	(0,383)	(0,386)	(0,383)
		0,148***						0,083				
		(0,053)						(0,078)				
			0,096**						-0,007			
			(0,044)						(0,067)			
				0,119**		0,114**				0,131*		0,131*
				(0,048)		(0,050)				(0,067)		(0,067)
					0,080	0,119 **					0,049	
					(0,060)	(0,054)					(0,092)	
R ²	0,002	0,052	0,080	0,116	0,126	0,113	0,002	0,010	0,010	0,027	0,033	0,027
F	0,173	2,752**	3,300**	3,936***	3,591***	4,785***	0,173	0,494	0,370	1,394	0,855	1,394
ΔF		7,893***	4,740**	6,042**	1,766	4,816**		1,135	0,011	3,831*	0,288	3,831*

	DEPENDABILITY						FLEXIBILITY					
	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3	MODEL 4	MODEL 5	MODEL 6	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 3	MODEL 4	MODEL 5	MODEL 6
CONSTANT	5,164***	4,057***	3,724***	3,710***	3,642***	3,634***	3,757***	3,260***	2,825***	2,807***	2,74***	2,820***
FIRM SIZE	(0,710)	(0,761)	(0,761)	(0,757)	(0,756)	(0,756)	(0,625)	(0,689)	(0,673)	(0,663)	(0,662)	(0,621)
TYPE OF INDUSTRY	0,056	0,003	-0,021	-0,027	-0,027	-0,023	0,164**	0,141*	0,110	0,102	0,101	0,102
CONTROL PRACTICES	(0,088)	(0,086)	(0,085)	(0,085)	(0,085)	(0,085)	(0,077)	(0,078)	(0,076)	(0,074)	(0,074)	(0,074)
INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN	-0,046	-0,070	-0,049	-0,113	-0,130	-0,095	0,353	0,342	0,369	0,283	0,267	0,283
INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS LOGISTICS PRACTICES	(0,361)	(0,349)	(0,344)	(0,344)	(0,343)	(0,342)	(0,318)	(0,316)	(0,304)	(0,301)	(0,301)	(0,300)
		0,241***				0,133*		0,108*				
		(0,071)				(0,078)		(0,064)				
			0,146**			0,107*			0,191***			0,150***
			(0,060)			(0,063)			(0,053)			(0,053)
				0,104						0,141**		0,142**
				(0,066)						(0,058)		(0,056)
					0,115	0,143*					0,100	
					(0,082)	(0,077)					(0,072)	
R ²	0,003	0,072	0,108	0,123	0,134	0,128	0,043	0,060	0,135	0,169	0,179	0,169
F	0,202	3,960***	4,568***	4,190***	3,847***	4,392***	3,432**	3,253**	5,906***	6,088***	5,428***	7,660***
ΔF		11,45***	6,000**	2,498	1,991	2,885*		2,813*	13,09***	6,028**	1,938	6,381**

Standard error in parentheses ***p<0,01 **p<0,05 *p<0,10

In the specific case of hypothesis 1, and to avoid misinterpretations deriving from the collinearity between advanced purchasing practices and to isolate their effect from that of the control variables, six regression models were estimated for each dependent variable. In the first model only the control variables were introduced as independent variables. Each of the four variables related to the implementation of advanced purchasing practices were incorporated, respectively and independently, to each of the following four models. In the sixth model the four types of practices were introduced together as independent variables, but the entry of these variables was conditioned by a stepwise procedure. This way, only those variables capable of explaining part of the variance of the dependent variable that the rest of the variables cannot explain are entered into the model. Table V shows the results of the estimation of all models for each of the dependent variables. In the case of hypothesis 2, only two regression models were considered. The first model only considers the control variables (firm size, type of industry) as independent variables, and the second model incorporates the degree of strategic integration of purchasing. Table VI shows the results of estimating these models.

Table VI: Regression of purchasing performance on the strategic integration of purchasing

	QUALITY		COST		DEPENDABILITY		FLEXIBILITY	
	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 1	MODEL 2	MODEL 1	MODEL 2
CONSTANT	5,638***	5,423***	5,609***	5,524***	5,164***	4,806***	3,757***	3,510***
	(0,520)	(0,517)	(0,756)	(0,767)	(0,710)	(0,699)	(0,625)	(0,623)
FIRM SIZE	0,037	0,039	-0,030	-0,029	0,056	0,059	0,164**	0,166**
	(0,064)	(0,063)	(0,093)	(0,093)	(0,088)	(0,085)	(0,077)	(0,076)
TYPE OF INDUSTRY	-0,059	-0,268	-0,163	-0,245	-0,046	-0,394	0,353	0,113
	(0,264)	(0,272)	(0,384)	(0,403)	(0,361)	(0,367)	(0,318)	(0,327)
STRATEGIC INTEGRATION		0,121**		0,048		0,201***		0,139**
		(0,047)		(0,069)		(0,063)		(0,056)
R2	0,002	0,044	0,002	0,005	0,003	0,065	0,043	0,080
F	0,173	2,341*	0,173	0,271	0,202	3,513**	3,432**	4,383***
ΔF		6,663**		0,470		10,111***		6,059**

Standard error in parentheses ***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.10

Hypothesis 3 suggests that the relationship between the strategic integration of the purchasing function and business performance is mediated by the implementation of advanced purchasing management practices. That is, the positive effect of the strategic integration of purchasing is channelled through the implementation of these practices. It makes sense, therefore, to test the hypothesis only for those performance dimensions related to the strategic integration of purchasing, that is, for cases where hypothesis 2 is

confirmed (Baron and Kenny, 1986). Consequently, the hypothesis was studied only for quality, reliability and flexibility performance. To avoid problems of interpretation deriving from collinearity, we chose to study a model for each dimension of performance and each dimension of advanced purchasing practices. We therefore studied 12 models by applying Structural Equation Modelling analysis using AMOS 5.0. This methodology has been considered the most powerful analytical technique for the study of mediation (Venkatraman, 1989). Table VII summarizes the results of the estimation of the different models. By way of illustration, the first of these is presented graphically in Figure 2.

Table VII: Goodness of fit indexes of models relating strategic integration, advanced purchasing practices and purchasing performance

		QUALITY					STRATEGIC I-> PURCHASING P. j	PURCHASING P. j-> QUALITY
		X ² /d.f.	GFI	RMSEA	AGFI	CFI		
		R.V. <=3	>=0.90	<=0.80	>=0.80	>=0.90		
MEDIATING VARIABLE	CONTROL PRACTICES	1,601	0,913	0,062	0,874	0,957	0,481***	0,268***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN	1,748	0,920	0,069	0,874	0,964	0,387***	0,166***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS	1,640	0,927	0,064	0,886	0,966	0,372***	0,240***
	LOGISTICS PRACTICES	1,603	0,911	0,062	0,871	0,959	0,483***	0,231***
		DEPENDABILITY					STRATEGIC I-> PURCHASING P. j	PURCHASING P. j-> DEPENDABILITY
MEDIATING VARIABLE	CONTROL PRACTICES	1,563	0,915	0,060	0,877	0,966	0,524***	0,369***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN	1,687	0,925	0,067	0,882	0,972	0,364***	0,250***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS	1,545	0,929	0,059	0,889	0,976	0,373***	0,300***
	LOGISTICS PRACTICES	1,439	0,920	0,053	0,884	0,975	0,480***	0,360***
		FLEXIBILITY					STRATEGIC I, j-> PURCHASING P. j	PURCHASING j ----> FLEXIBILITY
MEDIATING VARIABLE	CONTROL PRACTICES	1,736	0,914	0,069	0,870	0,954	0,546***	0,211***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCT DESIGN	1,981	0,920	0,080	0,867	0,962	0,386***	0,221***
	INVOLVEMENT IN PRODUCTION PROCESS	1,942	0,923	0,078	0,871	0,959	0,370***	0,352***
	LOGISTICS PRACTICES	1,619	0,922	0,063	0,883	0,964	0,500***	0,310***

R.V. (Recommended values based on Chau, 1997)

***p<0,01 **p<0,05 *p<0,10

To test hypothesis 4, we applied Moderated Regression Analysis (Sharma et al. 1981). First we created the interaction variables, computing the product of the strategic integration of purchasing variable (IE) and each dimension of advanced purchasing practices (PACj). For each pair (IE and PACj) and each dimension of purchasing performance we estimated four models: (1) introducing only the control variables (firm

size, industry type) as independent variables; (2) including PACj; (3) including IE; and (4) incorporating the interaction effect (IExPACj). To confirm the existence of positive effects of moderation, the fourth model should increase significantly the predictive power (R^2) and the interaction term should present a positive and significant coefficient in this model. If, moreover, in the third model the moderator variable (IE) has a significant coefficient, the effect is said to be of quasi-moderation, and if not, of pure moderation (Sharma et al. 1981). Table VIII shows the only case in which an effect of moderation was found after analyzing a total of 16 possibilities (4 pairs IE x PACj for each of the 4 dimensions of performance as dependent variable).

Figure 2: An example of an estimated mediation model

INDEX	X2(P)	X2/d.f.	GFI	RMSEA	AGFI	CFI
R.V*	P>0.05	<=3	>=0.90	<=0.08	>=0.80	>=0.90
Outcome	100.86 (0.002)	1.601	0.913	0.062	0.874	0.957

* Recommended values based on Chau (1997)

5. Results and discussion

As we can see in Table V, there is generally a positive relationship between the implementation of advanced purchasing practices and purchasing performance, which leads us to accept, in general terms, hypothesis 1. This result is consistent with a number of previous relevant studies (e.g. Carr and Pearson, 1999; Zsidisin and Ellram, 2001; Narisimhan and Das, 2001; Chen et al. 2004). In particular, we find that control practices and supplier involvement in product design have a positive and significant effect ($p < 0.10$) in all dimensions of purchasing performance except that related to cost. Supplier involvement in the production process maintains a positive relationship with three dimensions of purchasing performance (all except dependability). This leads us to believe that the control practices and supplier involvement in product design and production process practices are the advanced purchasing practices capable of improving performance in purchasing. In fact, each of these practices appears to be the one with the highest explanatory power in at least one of the performance variables (see model 6 for each dependent variable). The effect of logistic practices is, however, weaker and this could be the result of its collinearity with the other practices (in two performance dimensions model 6 presents a significant effect ' $p < 0.1$ ', these effects being non-existent in model 5).

Also, these results suggest that the advanced purchasing practices have a highly significant explanatory power over quality, dependability and flexibility performance, but are less powerful in explaining the performance dimension relative to cost. This suggests that the advanced purchasing practices tend to favour differentiation business strategies based on competitive priorities such as quality, dependability or flexibility rather than cost leadership strategies.

Table VI shows that the strategic integration of the purchasing function is positively related to the performance of that function, which allows us to accept hypothesis 2. In particular, we emphasize that strategic integration is related to three performance dimensions: quality, dependability and flexibility. However, no significant evidence was found for cost performance. As observed with some advanced purchasing practices while testing hypothesis 1, the strategic integration of purchasing functions appears to be associated with differentiation strategies based on quality, dependability or flexibility rather than cost leadership strategies.

Again, this idea is consistent with the arguments of those works that defend the strategic importance of the purchasing function (e.g. Ellram and Carr, 1994; Sánchez-Rodríguez, 2009). Some companies believe that this role is purely administrative and that its main activity is based on best price selection and cost control. However, in recent years an increasing number of companies recognize the strategic importance of the purchasing function and its potential to support and develop other competitive strategies based on differentiation.

Table VII shows an acceptable goodness of fit for the 12 estimated models. In all the models, a significant path from strategic integration to each performance dimension appears through each advanced purchasing practice. The data therefore strongly support the hypothesis for three of the performance dimensions. This result is consistent with the approach of Narasimhan and Das, (2001) and Chen et al. (2004), who argued a significant predictive power of the strategic integration of purchasing over the implementation of advanced purchasing practices, taking into account that the implementation of these practices enhances and develops the role of purchasing and improves its performance.

To check the robustness of the results we incorporated all the variables into a single model according to the scheme shown in Figure 3. On the one hand, the different advanced practices were merged in a single second-order construct called “advanced purchasing practices”. On the other hand, a second-order latent construct called “purchasing differentiation” was considered to capture the essence of the three dimensions of performance (quality, dependability and flexibility). The results of testing this aggregated model confirm the individual reports: advanced practices play a mediating role in the relationship between the strategic integration of the purchasing function and the performance achieved by that function.

Finally, as shown in Table VIII, an only one case of pure moderation of strategic integration was found, that which relates the logistics practices to costs performance. This suggests that the strategic integration of purchasing affects the relationship between logistics practices and costs performance, and does so by increasing the impact of logistics on the costs performance. However, the effect seems to be an isolated event and thus does not allow us to strongly confirm hypothesis 4. The results thus lead us to revise our initial model (Figure 1) and propose a new model that appears in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Estimation of an aggregated model of relationships between the variables

Table VIII: Moderating effect of strategic integration: significant results of moderated regression analyses

INDEPENDENT VARIABLES			COEFFICIENTS						R ²	F	ΔF
			CONSTANT	SIZE FIRM	TYPE OF INDUSTRY	β ₁	β ₂	β ₃			
LOGISTICS PRACTICES			5,267***	-0,046	-0,196	0,101			0,014	0,738	1,868
LOGISTICS PRACTICES	STRATEGIC INTEGRATION		5,266***	-0,046	-0,204	0,098	0,005		0,014	0,551	0,004
LOGISTICS PRACTICES	STRATEGIC INTEGRATION	LOGISTICS x STRATEGIC I.	8,113***	-0,031	-0,260	-0,577*	-0,549**	0,130**	0,048	1,526	5,362**

***p<0,01 **p<0,05 *p<0,10

Figure 4: Revised model

6. Conclusions

From a theoretical point of view, this research has provided evidence that supports the existence of a positive effect of advanced purchasing practices on purchasing performance. That is, the results suggest that the implementation of advanced purchasing practices such as supplier control, supplier involvement in product design, supplier involvement in the production process or logistics integration significantly contributes to better performance in aspects such as the quality, the flexibility or the dependability of the supply chain. The relationship between advanced purchasing practices and cost performance was also tested, but no significant evidence was found for that case. This suggests that the implementation of advanced purchasing practices tends to favour the implementation of differentiation strategies based on quality, dependability and flexibility at the expense of cost leadership strategies.

The fact that advanced purchasing practices contribute positively to better performance in supply management ratifies the importance of inter-firm cooperation, based on

strengthening the relationship between buyers and suppliers. Such cooperation, as posed by the resource-based theory of the firm, is a strategy used by companies to access resources of other companies and to develop and retain their own resources and combine them with those of their suppliers in order to generate competitive advantage (Das and Teng, 2000). Therefore, a synergic effect would appear between the cooperating parties, thus leading to the creation of networks of companies that enjoy the benefits of flexibility that this reticular structure generates and become enriched with the shared knowledge of the organizations that comprise them (Barney, 1991). Likewise, the high correlation between the implementation of the various advanced practices suggests that the simultaneous application of all of them can generate other kinds of synergies that may improve the results achieved with their individual implementation. This idea is consistent with the studies of Flynn et al. (1999), who concluded that there are more synergies in the so called world class manufacturers that are not present in other companies, mainly because the combined use of world class practices can simultaneously improve their performance in various aspects such as cost, quality, flexibility and dependability.

Similarly, we can conclude that the strategic integration of purchasing exerts a positive effect on purchasing performance. This effect takes place through the implementation of advanced purchasing practices. As the purchasing function gains strategic relevance in the organization, its capacity to acquire resources grows and this allows it to develop more sophisticated practices. One might also think that the success attributed in recent years to these practices has led to the strategic recognition of the purchasing function and its integration in the design and deployment of business strategies. In any case, the results show the existence of an important link between both factors, the level of integration of the purchasing function and the implementation of advanced purchasing practices, resulting in better performance of the purchasing function.

From a practical point view, top managers should take into account the need to involve the purchasing function in the strategic planning process of the firm, so that the decisions taken in that function are consistent and aligned with the organizational objectives and the initiatives undertaken by other functional areas. We recommend, therefore, that the purchasing function should be recognized within the organizational structure at the same level as other functional areas and its status should be comparable with regard to resource allocation and access to strategic decision-making. We believe, based on the empirical

results obtained, that this measure can help the company develop capabilities on which to base a sustainable competitive advantage.

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